

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The influence of social media use on adolescent mental health: A literature review

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Abstract

During adolescence, everyone undergoes a crucial developmental phase in forming a strong foundation of health, ranging from rapid physical, cognitive, and psychosocial growth, which has a significant impact on adolescent mental health. Adolescents are among the highest rate of internet use with the main reason being access to social media. Social media provides a vast platform for adolescents to connect with friends, share experiences, and express themselves. However, questions surrounding the impact of social media use on adolescents' mental health are increasingly becoming the focus of attention. This literature study aims to find out more about the influence of social media use on adolescents' mental health. This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach. The type of research used is literature review or literature study. Data searches were conducted in the Google Scholar and PubMed databases. Based on the results of the literature search, there were 7 articles that fit the criteria. There are various views on the influence of social media use on adolescent mental health. Social media use has a significant influence on adolescents' mental health with differing opinions in the literature, with some stating positive impacts, while others highlighting negative impacts. To overcome the negative impacts, judicious use of social media is key.

Keywords: Adolescents; Mental Health; Social Media; Influence; Impact

1. Introduction

Health is a fundamental need required by all individuals. Good health refers to optimal physical, mental, and social well-being, not simply the absence of disease or disability [1]. Mental health is a state of well-being in which a person has an awareness of his or her potential, can manage the stresses of life, works efficiently, and is able to make useful contributions to his or her community.

Adolescents are the age group between 10-19 years old [2]. According to the Indonesian Health Regulation No. 25 Year 2014, adolescents are the population aged 10-18 years. Meanwhile, BKKBN states that adolescents are the age group of 10-24 years and are not married [3]. Adolescents experience a stage of human development that is vital in forming a solid foundation of health [2]. While in adolescence, they experience rapid physical, cognitive, and psychosocial growth, which impacts their feelings, thinking, decision-making, and interactions with the world around them. This has a significant impact on adolescent mental health. Worldwide, estimates suggest that about 1 in every 7 individuals aged between 10 and 19 years, or about 14%, experience mental health problems. The estimated number of adolescents affected is around 166 million individuals, with 89 million males and 77 million females. Anxiety and depression are the most prevalent mental health problems among adolescents [4,5]. Results from the I-NAMHS (Indonesian National Adolescent Mental Health Survey) study indicate that by 2022, approximately 15.5 million Indonesian adolescents, equivalent to 34.9%, experienced at least one mental health problem in the past 12 months [6].

The use of social media has grown rapidly around the world, and Indonesia is no exception. This development has experienced changes in the way teenagers interact socially and communicate, especially among teenagers. According to

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survey data conducted by the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) in early 2023, the group of respondents aged between 13 to 18 years old had the highest internet usage rate, reaching 98.20%, followed by the 19 to 34 age group which reached 97.17%. Meanwhile, students and college students ranked first in terms of internet usage with a percentage of around 98.88%. The main reason for using the internet is access to social media [7]. Social media provides a broad platform for teenagers to connect with friends, share experiences, and express themselves. However, the question surrounding the impact of social media use on adolescent mental health is increasingly the focus of attention.

This literature study aims to find out more about the influence of social media use on adolescent mental health. In such a dynamic digital age, understanding how social media can affect adolescents' mental well-being is becoming increasingly important. By examining recent research and findings, this article will attempt to summarize key findings that address the impact of social media use on adolescent mental health.

2. Material and methods

This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach. Data sources for this research come from references such as journals, books, and other written sources. The type of research used is literature review or literature study, which is a research method that seeks to explain or describe the literature relevant to a particular topic or domain. This literature review provides an analysis of what has been presented by previous researchers, the theories and hypotheses that support them, the proposed research problem, and the appropriate research methodology. The selection stage was carried out to obtain articles that fit the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data searches were conducted in the Google Scholar database and PubMed. Data were collected from content analysis of social media articles with adolescent mental health with the keywords "social media and adolescent mental health". Inclusion criteria included were published in 2018 - 2023. The exclusion criteria were articles that could not be accessed in full text. At the initial stage, 16,800 results were found on Google Scholar and 600 results on PubMed. There were 14 articles analyzed from dozens of articles that had been identified based on title, abstract and research design. Then, articles were selected based on compatibility with the discussion in this study and following the criteria, thus 7 articles were used for literature review in this study.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results of the literature search, there were 7 articles that fit the criteria. There are various views on the influence of social media use on adolescent mental health, including those that have been collected based on several previous studies as follows:

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Method	Result
1	Rosmalina and Khaerunisa [8]	Scoping review	There is a relationship between mental health and social media use in adolescents.
2	Yuhana et al. [9]	Correlational analytic	A total of 120 respondents (41.2%) frequently uses social media. 197 respondents (67.7%) had mental health problems. The use of social media affects the mental health of adolescents at SMAN 8 Semarang.
3	Thursina [10]	Explanatory research	This study resulted in 53% of adolescents who were identified with moderate mental health related to social media. Although most students have moderate mental health according to the study, with 53% impact of social media use on mental health, attention to this is important because adolescents are in a crucial transition phase. Anxiety disorders, stress, depression, and loneliness are dominant in adolescence, so it is necessary to continue to make various preventive efforts to be wise in using social media.
4	Pratama and Sari [11]	Observational analytic research with cross sectional approach	The intensity of social media use has a social impact on adolescents, namely the emergence of mental health disorders in the form of apathy. The correlation value is 0.528 and the significance value of $p < 0.001 < 0.05$ with a positive relationship direction so that the higher the level of intensity of social media use, the more apathetic the attitude of adolescents.

5	Septiana [12]	Explanatory design	There is an influence between social media use and adolescents' mental health and social well-being during the Covid-19 pandemic.
6	Abi-Jaoude et al. [13]	Qualitative design	Research indicates a concerning link between digital media use and negative mental health outcomes, particularly among youth. The design of social media platforms may contribute to behavioral reinforcement and addiction. Banning teenagers' use of social media is not an effective solution in addressing the potential harms associated with it. Instead, we should recognize that online interactions are a very important part of the development of today's teenagers. They have grown up in a highly connected and digitized world, and social media is part of their daily lives.
7	O'Reilly et al. [14]	Scoping review	Adolescents perceived social media as a threat to mental well-being and three themes were identified namely: social media is believed to cause mood and anxiety disorders for some adolescents, social media is perceived as a platform for cyberbullying, and social media use itself is often framed as a kind of 'addiction'.

All the literature found states that there is an influence of social media use on adolescent mental health. However, in each literature there are various opinions where some state that the influence of social media use has a positive impact, and some are negative.

Generally, social media can facilitate various kinds of things that gives positive impacts. Arnie (2015) in Rosmalina and Khaerunnisa [8] explains that social media makes it easy to find information, disseminate and share content. Social media also makes it easy to interact with anyone (family or friends) without being limited by distance. Social media can make it easier to create a community and express together. This impact applies to adolescents and can strengthen adolescents' personal development. This was found in the results of research by Yuhana et al. [9] and Thursina [10] on high school students. In the results of research by Yuhana et al. [9] stated that female students use social media more often than males, which is supported by Barus (2015) in Yuhana et al. [9] where women's active involvement in social media refers to women's ability to more freely express themselves, participate intensively in various activities such as entertaining themselves, finding friends, feeling happy, self-expression, and searching for information. The results of Thursina's research [10] also state that students feel happy with the existence of social media because they can keep up with current developments. During the COVID-19 pandemic, it was stated that the use of social media had a positive impact on adolescents with the result that there was an increase in mental health and social well-being [12].

Social media use also has a negative impact on adolescents' mental health. In the results of a review conducted by Abi-Jaoude et al. [13] stated that there are many studies that support that the use of smartphones and social media increases mental distress, self-harm, and suicide among adolescents. Social media, which is often used by adolescents as a place of self-expression, can cause mental health problems. Social media can affect adolescents' self-view and interpersonal relationships through social comparison and negative interactions, including cyberbullying [13,14]. This is supported by the results of research by Yuhana et al [9] where adolescents who use social media > 3 hours per day experience self-concept problems, where the decline in self-concept in adolescents due to feelings of insecurity and comparing themselves with friends who are on social media. Not only that, but some students also admit that they seek existence and want to be recognized through social media, causing stress. The existence of social media has many moments for families or couples to publish social media, at that time there is also loneliness, anxiety and depression for students who do not feel this. Social media social media content often involves the normalization and even promotion of self-harm and suicide among adolescents. This is supported in Rosmalina and Khaerunnisa [8] explained that social media can cause envy from other users who show off their daily activities and the emergence of shame due to being humiliated on social media. There is research results Yuhana et al. [9] showed that there is a relationship between social media use and adolescent mental health at SMA N 8 Semarang with most of SMAN 8 Semarang students often using social media and having health problems in the disorder category. The health problems were recognized by students to be disturbed in their daily activities, where they lost their appetite and had difficulty sleeping. As many as 44.3% of adolescents used social media before going to bed and as many as 55% of adolescents felt that they could not sleep well [9].

When teens use social media intensively, it can affect their social life. In a day, 22% of teens log into their favorite social media more than 10 times [11]. Excessive use of social media can have an impact on student learning behavior, such as decreased motivation to learn and reduced creativity in the school environment [9]. Adolescents who use social media

excessively will make them focus on themselves and their own world, which can lead to social media addiction. Adolescents see social media as a potential threat to mental wellbeing because social media use is often described as a form of 'addiction' [14]. This results in the emergence of apathy, reduced socialization with people around [11] often experiencing depression, stress, anxiety, and feeling lonely, social isolation [9].

Adolescent use of social media can potentially lead to mental health problems, such as anxiety disorders and depression, especially when not used wisely [8]. Some students from Thursina's study [10] realized that social media use should be tailored to their individual personalities, with preventive measures that include limiting social media use, utilizing it for learning purposes, doing positive activities, and behaving wisely. In this case, self-control, emotion regulation, and a wise attitude in using social media are important keys to obtaining positive benefits from its use [12]. Collaboration between clinicians, adolescents, and families is also needed to address the potential harms of social media and smartphone use, including through education and appropriate solutions [13].

4. Conclusion

Social media use has a significant influence on adolescents' mental health. There are differing opinions in the literature, with some citing positive impacts, while others highlight negative impacts. In a positive context, social media facilitates information seeking, content sharing, social interaction, and community building. Social media also allows adolescents to express themselves and strengthen their personal development. On the other hand, excessive use of social media also has a negative impact on adolescents' mental health. This includes issues such as anxiety disorders, depression, insecurity, and stress. Excessive social media use influences adolescents' mental health. To overcome the negative impacts, being mindful of social media use is key. This includes limiting social media use, using it for learning purposes, adopting positive behaviors, and having self-control and emotion regulation. Collaboration between clinicians, adolescents and families is also needed to reduce the potential harm of social media use, through education and appropriate solutions. Thus, it is important to assess and manage the impact of social media use on adolescent mental health wisely.

Compliance with ethical standards

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